

The Bangladesh Patents Act, 2023

(Act No. 53 of 2023)

Monday, November 13, 2023

Bangladesh National Parliament

Dhaka, 28 Kartika, 1430 / November 13, 2023

The following act, adopted by the Parliament, has received the President's assent on November 13, 2023, corresponding to 28 Kartika, 1430, and is hereby published for the information of the general public:

Act No. 53 of 2023

An Act Enacted to Repeal the Bangladesh Patents Act, 2022 and to Newly Formulate Law Recognizing the Importance of Matters Related to Patents

WHEREAS it is expedient and necessary to repeal the Bangladesh Patents Act, 2022 (Act No. 05 of 2022) and to formulate a new law recognizing the importance of matters related to patents;

It is hereby enacted as follows:-

Chapter One

Preliminary

Short Title and Commencement	<p>1. (1) This Act may be called the <i>Bangladesh Patents Act, 2023</i>.</p> <p>(2) It shall come into force on such date as the Government may, by notification in the official Gazette, determine.</p> <p><i>Provided that the Government may, if necessary, specify different dates for the commencement of different provisions of this Act.</i></p>
Definitions	<p>2. Unless there is anything repugnant in the subject or context, in this Act—</p> <p>(1) "<i>Priority date</i>" means the earliest date of filing of a patent application in any country worldwide;</p>

(2) "*Priority claim*" means a claim of priority as declared under Section 5 of this Act;

(3) "*Directorate*" means the Department of Patents, Industrial Designs, and Trademarks (DPDT);

(4) "*Court*" means the court referred to in Section 3 of the *Civil Courts Act, 1887* (Act No. XII of 1887);

(5) "*Exclusive license*" means a license granted by the patent holder that confers exclusive rights over the patented invention to the licensee and any individual authorized by the licensee, and includes the exclusive licensee;

(6) "*Invention*" means a new product or process associated with an inventive step and applicable in industry, and not disqualified from patentability under this Act;

(7) "*Inventive step*" means such a characteristic of an invention that reflects technical advancement over existing knowledge, is beyond prior art, and is not obvious to a person skilled in the relevant field of technology;

(8) "*Prior art*" means information related to the invention made publicly available in any form, whether written, oral, or otherwise, in any location worldwide before the priority date by publication, demonstration, use, or other means;

(9) "*Civil procedure*" means the *Code of Civil Procedure, 1908* (Act No. V of 1908);

(10) "*Novelty*" means an invention that is not visibly available to the public through publication, prior use, or exhibition and does not form part of prior art. It is also not derived from any known components, including those in granted or published patent applications;

(11) "*Patent*" means the right granted for an invention under Section 25 of this Act;

(12) "*Patent agent*" means a person registered as a patent agent under this Act;

(13) "*Patentee*" means any individual who holds the patent rights under this Act;

	<p>(14) "<i>Person</i>" includes any natural person, government, company, association, or group, whether incorporated or not;</p> <p>(15) "<i>Matter</i>" includes any general object and also encompasses biological resources;</p> <p>(16) "<i>Rules</i>" means the rules framed under this Act;</p> <p>(17) "<i>Director General</i>" means the Director General of the Department of Patents, Industrial Designs, and Trademarks;</p> <p>(18) "<i>Licensee</i>" means a person licensed to use a patent granted under this Act;</p> <p>(19) "<i>Capable of Industrial Application</i>" means an invention—</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) that enables the production of a product or the application of a technical process as claimed in the patent; (b) that has known utility, as without it, practical application would not exist; (c) that contains technical or technological attributes, as without these it would not relate to industry; and (d) that is disclosed in a way that allows a person with ordinary skills to achieve the invention without engaging in any inventive activity; <p>(20) "<i>Assignee</i>" includes a person appointed as the assignee by the patent holder or the legal representative of a deceased patent holder, and when referred to, includes any legal representative or assignee appointed by the assignee;</p> <p>(21) "<i>Interested person</i>" means any person who is directly or indirectly affected by the grant of a patent for an invention.</p>
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Chapter Two

Directorate of Patents, Industrial Designs, and Trademarks, Patent Applications, etc.

Directorate	<p>3. For the purposes of this Act, the term <i>Department of Patents, Industrial Designs, and Trademarks</i> (DPDT) shall refer to the Department of Patents, Industrial Designs, and Trademarks established under Section 3 of the <i>Bangladesh Industrial Designs Act, 2023</i> (Act No. 22 of 2023).</p>
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<p style="text-align: center;">Persons Entitled to Apply for a Patent</p>	<p>4. The following persons shall be entitled to apply for a patent:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Any person who, as the rightful and first inventor, claims the invention through an application; b) An assignee of the rightful and first inventor associated with the invention in the patent application; c) A legal representative of a deceased person who, immediately before their death, was entitled to make such an application; d) If two or more persons jointly invent a patentable subject matter, all such persons shall have rights to the patent; e) If two or more persons independently create the same invention, the person who first applies for the patent shall hold the right to that patent, and in the case of a priority claim, the priority date shall be considered the filing date of the patent application; f) Patent rights may be transferred or assigned by inheritance; g) In cases where an employee invents something under a contractual employment agreement, unless explicitly stated otherwise in the contract, the right to the patent shall be vested in the employer; h) Where an employee, outside of an invention-specific contract, uses the employer's equipment, data, know-how, and other resources to create an invention, the right to the patent shall be vested in the employer unless specified otherwise in the employment contract.
<p style="text-align: center;">Priority Date of Complete Specification</p>	<p>5. Each claim within a complete specification shall have the following priority date:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) If a complete specification is submitted following a provisional application, the filing date of the provisional application shall be considered the priority date. (b) If a complete specification is filed within 12 (twelve) months based on a previously filed application in Bangladesh, and the claim is appropriately based on the disclosed subject matter in the prior application, then the date of first disclosure in the previously filed application shall serve as the priority date. (c) If a complete specification is filed in relation to a re-filed application, and the claim is appropriately based on subject matter first disclosed in a previous specification, whether provisional or complete, then the filing date of the specification in which the subject matter was first disclosed shall be considered the priority date. (d) If a complete specification under this section has two or more priority dates, the earliest of these dates shall be regarded as the priority date.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (e) The priority period shall be 12 (twelve) months, counted from the date of the first application filing. (f) Where a priority claim is made under this section, the Director-General may instruct the applicant to submit, within a prescribed time, a certificate of verification issued by the intellectual property office where the previous application was filed. (g) For the purpose of fulfilling this section, any additional necessary matters shall be prescribed by rules.
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Chapter Three

Non-Patentable Inventions

<p>Non-Patentable Matters</p>	<p>6. (1) The following items shall be excluded from the scope of patent protection:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) Discoveries, scientific theories, and mathematical methods; (b) Business methods, methods of purely mental acts, rules or methods of games, and any associated computer program or algorithm; (c) Methods of treatment of human or animal bodies through surgery or therapy, as well as diagnostic methods applied to human or animal bodies; (d) The partial or complete use of any known substance or naturally occurring biological material, any new use of them, or any method of use (including sequence); (e) Plants and animals, in whole or in part, modified or unmodified (including seeds, varieties, species, and essential biological processes necessary for the production of plants and animals, as well as microbiological processes), or any substance, organism, or biological resource found in nature (whether in whole or in part, and even if purified, isolated, or modified), including its genome, germplasm, gene, cell, protein, sequence, cell line, cell culture, or any other component, except for man-made microorganisms; (f) Any invention whose primary or potential use or commercial application is contrary to public order and morality or poses serious harm to human, animal, or plant life or health or to the environment; (g) Any invention that is trivial or frivolous, or any process that is established and demonstrably contrary to natural laws;
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	<p>(h) Any item obtained through mere combination or aggregation of known components, or any structure where the properties of its elements are combined, and any method of producing such an item;</p> <p>(i) Any arrangement or reproduction of multiple known devices, which retain their individual properties independently effective before arrangement;</p> <p>(j) Methods of agriculture or horticulture;</p> <p>(k) Literary, dramatic, musical, or artistic works, cinematographic works, and radio or television programs;</p> <p>(l) Descriptions of information only;</p> <p>(m) Detailed descriptions related to integrated circuits composed of various components;</p> <p>(n) Any invention that is effectively traditional knowledge or any combination or aggregation of known properties of traditional elements or substances;</p> <p>(o) The mere discovery of a known substance in a new form, or the mere discovery of new properties or new uses of a known substance, or the mere discovery of a new method of use of a known process, machine, or device unless such process results in the production of at least one new element in a new reaction or product.</p> <p>Explanation: For the purposes of this clause, salts, esters, ethers, polymorphs, metabolites, pure forms, particle sizes, isomers, isomer mixtures, complexes, compositions, and other derivatives obtained from known substances shall be considered equivalent substances;</p> <p>(p) Any claim describing alternatives that can be defined by a general formula, characterized by one or more configurations, subsets, or sub-ranges, along with the common function, property, or invention, which are within a larger known set or range disclosed in prior art.</p> <p>(2) In accordance with the decisions of the Council for <i>Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights</i> (TRIPs), hereinafter referred to as the TRIPs Council, pharmaceutical and agrochemical products shall remain excluded from patent protection for as long as the exemption period for such products remains effective:</p> <p>Provided, however, that the government may, if necessary, extend or reduce the said period through notification in the official Gazette.</p>
<p>Non-Patentability</p>	<p>7. No patent shall be granted for any inventions related to the production, control, use, or extraction of atomic energy, or for the exploration, mining,</p>

of Inventions Related to Atomic Energy	extraction, production, natural and chemical processing, construction, development, storage, or use of any specified or radioactive materials, or for ensuring safety in the operation of atomic energy.
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Chapter Four

Application for Grant of Patent

Procedure for Patent Application	<p>8. (1) For a single invention, only one application for a patent may be submitted, in the prescribed form, to the Directorate.</p> <p>(2) In an application submitted under subsection (1), it must be stated whether the invention is in the possession of the applicant, and the name of the true and first inventor should be included. If the claimant is not the applicant or one of the joint applicants, the application must include a declaration stating that the applicant believes the named person to be the true and first inventor.</p> <p>(3) The following documents must be attached to the patent application:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) A copy of the power of attorney under the Power of Attorney Act, 2012 (Act No. 35 of 2012) if the applicant submits the application through a representative; (b) A certificate or assignment letter justifying the applicant’s right if the applicant is not the inventor; (c) A certified copy in cases of a priority claim, under section 5(c) of this Act. <p>(4) A claimant may apply for a patent in the prescribed form and method with the Director General, including either a complete specification or a provisional specification, subject to the following conditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) A complete specification must be submitted within 12 (twelve) months from the filing of the provisional specification by the applicant; (b) The provisional specification should contain the general characteristics of the invention and must be consistent with the subsequently submitted complete specification. <p>(5) The form submitted under subsection (1) shall include the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) Full details regarding the names and identities of the applicant and inventor;
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- (b) An appropriate title related to the invention's subject matter;
- (c) A clear and comprehensive description of the invention for which the patent is sought;
- (d) If the Director General determines that a particular model or sample explaining or forming the invention should be attached to the application, the applicant must submit it before filing for the patent; however, such a model or sample shall not be considered part of the specification;
- (e) An abstract summarizing the invention;
- (f) The number and date of the priority claim, if applicable;
- (g) Written details of the invention in the complete specification.

(6) Each complete specification must include:

- (a) A full, clear, and concise description, allowing a skilled person in the relevant or similar technology to evaluate, perform, comply with, implement, or operate every aspect of the invention;
- (b) A detailed description of each step or method of implementing the invention, including the best method known to the applicant at the time of filing or at the priority date;
- (c) One or more claims specifying the features of the invention claimed for protection;
- (d) Technical information of the invention in the abstract;
- (e) Except in special cases, the abstract shall not exceed 300 (three hundred) words:

Provided that the Director General may amend the abstract for further clarification to a third party.

(7) The subject matter of the invention:

- (a) Must be stated in claim format,
- (b) Must be clear and concise and fully supported by the description,
- (c) May be described with illustrations or diagrams as needed.

(8) If specified in the application or otherwise, the applicant must disclose all relevant prior art known to them at the time of the application or priority date to the Director General, as necessary for determining patentability.

(9) If the invention relates to a pharmaceutical product, the applicant shall disclose its International Nonproprietary Name (INN) at the priority date if available; otherwise, the applicant shall inform the

	<p>Director General within 30 (thirty) days. If the patent application is rejected or the patent expires, such disclosure of the name will not be required.</p> <p>(10) The scope of patent protection shall be limited to the disclosed and explicitly claimed use, purpose, or operation in the patent.</p> <p>(11) One or more claims of a complete specification shall pertain to a single invention or a group of interconnected inventions that form a single inventive concept and shall be based on the subject matter disclosed in the specification.</p> <p>(12) If, at the time of application acceptance, the Director General finds that the requirements specified in subsections (5), (6), (8), (9), (10), and (11) have not been fulfilled, they shall instruct the applicant to make necessary amendments within a specified period, failing which the application shall be considered abandoned.</p> <p>(13) The source and geographical origin of biological resources and elements of traditional knowledge associated with them, directly or indirectly used in the claimed invention, shall be specified in the description of the invention.</p> <p>(14) The Director General may, for the dissemination of patented technology within Bangladesh, direct any foreign patent applicant to adapt the description of their patent in a manner suitable for the general competency level of the citizens of Bangladesh, prior to granting the patent.</p> <p>(15) A declaration regarding ownership of the invention must be attached in the prescribed form along with the complete specification, in specified cases or within the prescribed time following the submission of the complete specification.</p>
<p>Applications Related to Microorganisms</p>	<p>9. (1) If an invention relates to a microorganism, the applicant must deposit a culture of it in a designated depository institution in Bangladesh before filing the application. This is required if a person with ordinary skill in the relevant field within Bangladesh cannot execute the invention without such a culture, and if the product is not otherwise easily accessible to the public. Authorized parties may use the culture sample in accordance with the law, under the condition of proper use.</p>

	<p>(2) Applications filed under subsection (1) shall comply with the following requirements:</p> <p>(a) The product must be deposited in the specified depository institution before the patent application is filed in Bangladesh, and this fact must be noted in the specification within the designated time frame;</p> <p>(b) The specification must include all existing characteristics necessary for identifying or specifying the product, as well as the name, address, and deposit date of the depository institution, along with the product's unique deposit number at that institution;</p> <p>(c) The deposited product must be accessible at the depository institution only after the filing date of the patent application in Bangladesh, or after the priority date if a priority claim is made;</p> <p>(d) The source and geographical origin of biological resources and any associated traditional knowledge elements used in the claimed invention must be clearly mentioned in the specification.</p>
<p>Withdrawal and Reapplication of Patent</p>	<p>10. (1) The applicant may withdraw their submitted application at any time before it is granted.</p> <p>(2) In cases where:</p> <p>(a) The application is withdrawn before it is made available for public inspection;</p> <p>(b) No priority claim is made;</p> <p>(c) There are no ongoing proceedings in Bangladesh concerning any rights related to the application,</p> <p>a reapplication for the invention may be submitted.</p> <p>(3) An application submitted in Bangladesh shall be considered the first application, and if a reapplication is filed under clause (c) of subsection (2), no priority claim can be made based on the first application.</p>
<p>Application Amendment and Unity of Innovation</p>	<p>11. (1) Applications, complete specifications, or any related documents may not be amended except through renunciation, modification, or clarification. No amendment will be permitted for any purpose other than to incorporate the original subject matter.</p> <p>(2) No amendment will be approved in the complete specification if, as a result, the revised specification claims or describes any matter not previously disclosed or exhibited in the original specification.</p>

	<p>(3) If an application for amendment of the specification or any related documents is approved by the Director General or, as applicable, by the court after the patent has been granted:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) The amendment will be considered part of the specification and related documents for all purposes; (b) The amended specification and related documents shall be published as soon as possible; and (c) No question regarding the applicant's or patent holder's right to amend the patent shall be raised unless on grounds of fraud. <p>(4) In interpreting an amended specification, reference shall first be made to the initially accepted specification.</p>
<p>Amendment of Application, Specification, or Any Document Filed with the Director General</p>	<p>12. (1) The Director General, subject to the provisions of section 11, may, upon receipt of an application in the prescribed form from an applicant or patent holder, grant permission to amend a patent application, specification, or any related document under the specified conditions. However, if there is an ongoing case involving patent infringement in a court or any action for the withdrawal of the patent in the district court, the Director General shall not issue any order to grant or reject the amendment of a patent, specification, or related document, whether the case or action is initiated before or after the filing of the amendment application.</p> <p>(2) The amendment application for the patent or complete specification or related document under this section must specify the nature of the proposed amendment and the detailed reasons for the application.</p> <p>(3) Once an application is published, any interested party may, within the prescribed period after publication, oppose it by giving notice to the applicant. If such a notice is issued within the specified time, the Director General will inform the applicant and provide both parties (the applicant and the opponent) an opportunity for a hearing before resolving the issue.</p> <p>(4) If an application under sub-section (3) is published, any interested party may, within the prescribed time, issue a notice to the opposing party, and if such notice is provided within the specified period, the Director General will inform the concerned party about the submission of the amendment application and provide both the party and the opponent an opportunity for a hearing before deciding whether to file a case.</p>

	<p>(5) The provisions of this section shall not affect any right related to the instructions issued by the Director General prior to the grant of a patent based on the amendment of the specification or any related documents.</p>
<p>Amendment of Specification Filed in the District Judge's Court</p>	<p>13. (1) In the case of a proceeding for the cancellation of a patent in the District Judge's Court, subject to the provisions of section 11, the court may, as it deems necessary, grant permission to the patent holder to amend the specification in the prescribed manner and subject to expenses, advertisement, or other conditions. If the court rules that the patent is invalid, instead of canceling the patent, it may allow the amendment of the specification under this section.</p> <p>(2) If an application is made for an order in court, the applicant must give notice of the application to the Director General, and in such cases, the applicant shall have the right to be heard by the Director General.</p> <p>(3) A copy of the order for amendment granted by the District Judge's Court to the patent holder shall be sent to the Director General, who, upon receiving it, will register it and mention it in the register.</p>
<p>Director General's Power to Division of Application</p>	<p>14. (1) When a person applies for a patent under this Act, or in response to an objection raised by the Director General regarding the disclosure of multiple inventions in a single specification, the applicant may file a Divisional Application for each of the inventions disclosed in the provisional or complete specification, with the intent to resolve the objection.</p> <p>However, it is stipulated that the divisional application must be filed within 3 years from the filing date of the original application, and a maximum of 3 divisional applications can be made.</p> <p>(2) A complete specification must be attached to the divisional application, but it must not include any matter that is not disclosed in the original specification, which is not essential to the invention.</p> <p>(3) In the case of amendments to the complete specification following the original or divisional application, the Director General may issue an order ensuring that no claim made in one application is included in any other.</p> <p>(4) A divisional application will be considered as filed on the same date as the original application, and where applicable, the priority date of the original application will be considered the priority date of the divisional application.</p>

	<p>(5) A divisional application will be treated similarly to the original application, and if filed within the prescribed period, it will be examined accordingly.</p>
<p>Foreign Patent Application Documents Information</p>	<p>15. (1) If an applicant, individually or jointly with another person, files an application in a country other than Bangladesh, or if another person files an application on their behalf, claiming a patent based on the applicant's invention or with their rights, the applicant must submit the following documents along with the application or within 90 (ninety) days after filing the application:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) A statement containing detailed information about the foreign application. (b) A copy of any document provided to the applicant related to the results of the examination and search of the foreign application. (c) A copy of the granted patent based on the foreign application. (d) A copy of the rejection of the foreign application, if applicable. (e) A copy of any notice of withdrawal or abandonment of the granted patent, if applicable. (f) Any court orders or decisions related to the cancellation, invalidation, amendment, or other actions on the foreign patent or application. <p>(2) If the applicant requests additional time for translation of the documents, the Director General may extend the period mentioned in sub-section (1) by a maximum of 60 (sixty) days.</p> <p>(3) The applicant must submit the documents mentioned in sub-section (1) every 6 months until the foreign patent is granted or rejected.</p> <p>(4) After receiving the information as per sub-section (3), the Director General will publish the details on the official website.</p> <p>(5) If the applicant fails to comply with the requirements of sub-sections (1) and (3) due to reasons beyond their control, the application will be considered as rejected.</p>
<p>Patent Application Filing Date</p>	<p>16. The Director General shall consider the date of acceptance of the patent application as the filing date of the patent application.</p>
<p>Patent Application Publication</p>	<p>17. (1) After 18 (eighteen) months from the filing of the patent application, the Director General shall make the patent application available for public inspection.</p>

	<p>(2) Under subsection (1), the content of the patent application shall be published on the official website or through notification in the gazette to inform the public of the following details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">(a) The title of the invention;(b) The name, address, and nationality of the patent applicant and inventor;(c) The filing date and number of the application;(d) The priority number and date, if any;(e) The classification of the patent;(f) The main drawings or diagrams of the invention, if applicable;(g) A summary of the subject matter. <p>(3) Until the patent application is published on the official website or in a gazette notice, the Director General shall not provide any third party access to inspect the application or disclose any information related to the patent application.</p> <p>(4) Before the expiration of the 18 (eighteen) month period, upon the applicant's request and payment of the prescribed fee, the Director General may make the patent application available for public inspection.</p> <p>(5) The applicant shall not file any infringement action until the patent is granted.</p>
<p>National Security-Related Patent Applications</p>	<p>18. (1) Any patent application related to national security shall be kept confidential, and if the Director General deems an application to be related to national security, the application shall be forwarded to the appropriate authority for verification regarding national security concerns.</p> <p>(2) The appropriate authority shall inform the Director General within 90 (ninety) days of receiving the national security-related application whether the claimed invention is related to national security. If the Director General is not notified within this period, the patent application shall be published.</p>

	<p>(3) The applicant shall not file any national security-related patent application abroad until notified by the Director General regarding the matter, or until the time limit under subsection (2) has passed.</p> <p>(4) Any invention related to national security shall not be used, licensed, or transferred without the approval of the appropriate authority.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Opposition Before Patent Grant</p>	<p>19. (1) After the publication of a patent application under Section 17(2) of this Act, but before the patent is granted, any person may oppose the patent. However, it is a condition that the patent shall not be granted within 6 (six) months from the date of publication.</p> <p>(2) The notice of opposition must identify the patent application being opposed, state the grounds of opposition, and provide sufficient supporting evidence.</p> <p>(3) The person opposing the patent application may raise the following issues:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) The invention claimed in the complete specification has been claimed in another complete specification either before or after the priority date, and an application has been filed in Bangladesh for that claim, and the priority date of that claim is earlier than the applicant’s priority date; b) The invention claimed in the complete specification was known to the public or used by the public before the priority date of that claim, either in Bangladesh or elsewhere, or if the provisions of Section 2(10) have not been complied with; c) The invention claimed in the complete specification is clearly demonstrated and, in consideration of what was published under Section 2(8) or used elsewhere, it does not involve an inventive step before the priority date, as per Section 2(7); d) The subject matter of the complete specification does not comply with the provisions of Section 2(19) or is not industrially applicable; e) The subject matter of the complete specification is not an invention under this Act, or is not patentable under Section 2(6); f) The subject matter of the complete specification is not an invention under this Act, or is not patentable under Section 6 of this Act; g) The invention or its method of use in the complete specification is not described fully and clearly according to the provisions of Sections 8(5), (6), (8), (9), (10), and (11);

	<p>h) The applicant has failed to disclose information to the Director General as per Section 15, or has provided false or incomplete information;</p> <p>i) The source and geographical origin of any biological resources used in the invention and any associated traditional knowledge have not been disclosed or have been incorrectly described;</p> <p>j) Based on oral or other forms of knowledge, it is presumed that the invention claimed in the complete specification already exists in the local or general community in Bangladesh or elsewhere.</p> <p>(4) The Director General shall publish the notice of opposition on the website or through other official channels.</p> <p>(5) The applicant may submit a rebuttal within a specified time period to refute the opposition.</p> <p>(6) The Director General may hold a hearing, allowing both the applicant and the opponent to present arguments or counterarguments.</p> <p>(7) Based on the written statements and evidence submitted by both the applicant and the opponent, and after hearing both parties, the Director General may:</p> <p>a) Reject the opposition;</p> <p>b) Order amendments to the complete specification and other documents before granting the patent;</p> <p>c) Refuse to grant the patent.</p> <p>(8) The Director General shall issue a written order with reasons and inform both parties of the decision within 1 (one) month after the dispute is resolved.</p>
<p>Opposition to Patent After Grant</p>	<p>20. (1) Under Section 24(2) of this Act, any interested party may submit a notice of opposition to the patent within 24 (twenty-four) months from the date of its publication on the official website, after the patent has been granted.</p> <p>(2) The notice of opposition must be submitted in the prescribed manner, and may be based on the following grounds:</p> <p>(a) The invention claimed in the complete specification has been claimed in another complete specification either before or after the priority date, and an application for the patent has been filed</p>

in Bangladesh for that claim, with the priority date of that claim being earlier than the applicant's priority date;

- (b) The invention claimed in the complete specification was known to the public or used by the public before the priority date of that claim, either in Bangladesh or elsewhere, or if the provisions of Section 2(10) have not been complied with;
- (c) The invention claimed in the complete specification is clearly demonstrated, and in consideration of what has been published under Section 2(8) or used elsewhere, it does not involve an inventive step before the priority date as per Section 2(7);
- (d) The subject matter of the complete specification is not in accordance with the provisions of Section 2(19) or is not industrially applicable;
- (e) The subject matter of the complete specification is not an invention under this Act, or is not patentable under Section 2(6);
- (f) The subject matter of the complete specification is not an invention under this Act, or is not patentable under Section 6 of this Act;
- (g) The invention or its method of use in the complete specification is not fully and clearly described according to the provisions of Sections 8(5), (6), (8), (9), (10), and (11);
- (h) The applicant has failed to disclose information to the Director General as per Section 15 or has submitted false or incomplete information on critical issues;
- (i) The source and geographical origin of any biological resources used in the invention and any associated traditional knowledge have not been disclosed or have been incorrectly described;
- (j) Based on oral or other forms of knowledge, it is presumed that the invention claimed in the complete specification already exists in the local or general community in Bangladesh or elsewhere.

(3) The Director General will provide the notice of opposition to the patent holder and publish it in the e-Gazette or on the official website.

(4) The patent holder may submit a rebuttal within a specified time period to refute the notice of opposition.

(5) The Director General will arrange a hearing, allowing both the patent holder and the opponent to present their oral and written evidence, arguments, and counterarguments. After the hearing, the Director General will decide whether to uphold, amend, or revoke the patent, and will inform both parties of the decision, along with the reasons, within one (1) month from the conclusion of the dispute.

<p style="text-align: center;">Request for Examination of Patent Application</p>	<p>21. (1) The applicant may request the examination of their patent application by the Director General, within 36 (thirty-six) months from the date of filing of the patent application, upon payment of the prescribed fee.</p> <p>(2) If no request for examination is made, the application will be considered abandoned.</p> <p>(3) Before the expiry of the time period mentioned in subsection (1), if a request for an extension of time along with the prescribed fee is submitted to the Director General, the time period mentioned in subsection (1) will be extended by 3 (three) months.</p> <p>(4) The Director General will make arrangements for the examination of the patent application in accordance with the provisions of this Act.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Examination of Application</p>	<p>22. (1) If a request for the examination of a patent application is made as described in subsection (1) of section 21, the application and specification, along with other relevant documents, shall be forwarded to the examiner as soon as possible, so that he can prepare a report addressing the following matters:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) Whether the application and specification, along with the relevant documents, comply with the provisions of this Act and the rules made under it. (b) Whether there is any legal ground for objection to the grant of the patent based on the application. (c) The results of the search conducted under section 23. (d) Any other matters as may be prescribed. <p>(2) If the examiner’s report on a patent application, as adopted by the Director General, is adverse to the applicant, and if it is necessary to amend the application and specification, along with the relevant documents, to ensure compliance with the procedures for the final decision, the Director General shall, as soon as possible, inform the applicant of the summary of objections, and, if requested by the applicant within the prescribed time, provide an opportunity for a hearing.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Patent Searching During Examination</p>	<p>23. (1) The person to whom a patent application is forwarded under section 22 shall conduct a search to verify the following aspects with respect to the claimed invention in the complete specification:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) Whether the invention, as described in section 2, meets the criteria of novelty, inventive step, and industrial applicability.

	<p>(b) Whether the conditions under subsection (1) of section 6 of this Act are fulfilled.</p> <p>(c) Whether the inventive step is adequately supported by evidence, comparative data, and appropriate documentation in the specification.</p> <p>(2) In addition to the search conducted under subsection (1), the examiner will also check whether the invention was disclosed in any document before the filing date of the complete specification, either in Bangladesh or elsewhere, to confirm whether it has been made public.</p> <p>(3) If any complete specification or any claim is amended before the grant of the patent under this Act, the amended specification or claim will undergo the same examination and search process as the original specification or claim.</p> <p>(4) The examination and search conducted under sections 22 and 23 shall not be considered as granting validity to any patent, and neither the examination, search, nor any related report or procedure shall impose any liability on the government or its officers concerning the validity of the patent or any related matter.</p>
<p>Granting, Refusal, and Modification of Patent</p>	<p>24. (1) After examining a patent application, if it is deemed that the invention satisfies the conditions for patent grant, and upon compliance with the provisions of section 19, the Director-General shall grant the patent by issuing an order. If the conditions are not met, the application shall be refused. In both cases, the Director-General shall inform the applicant in writing as soon as possible.</p> <p>(2) In the case of granting a patent, the Director-General shall take the following actions:</p> <p>(a) Publish the grant of the patent on the website or through a gazette notification.</p> <p>(b) Provide the applicant with the patent certificate, subject to the payment of the prescribed fee within the time period set by the regulations.</p> <p>(a) (c) Register the patent application in the patent register.</p>

Chapter 5

Patent Rights, Ownership, and Revocation

Rights of the Patent Holder	<p>25. Subject to the other provisions of this Act, the holder of a patent granted under this Act shall have the following rights:-</p> <p>(a) When the subject matter of the patent is a product, the patent holder shall have the exclusive right to prevent any third party from offering for sale, selling, producing, or importing such product into Bangladesh without the patent holder's consent.</p> <p>(b) When the subject matter of the patent is a process, the patent holder shall have the exclusive right to prevent any third party from using, applying, offering for sale, selling, or importing such process into Bangladesh without the patent holder's consent.</p>
Patent Date	<p>26. (1) Subject to the other provisions of this Act, the date of each patent shall be the date of filing the patent application or, where applicable, the priority date.</p> <p>(2) The date of each patent shall be recorded in the register.</p>
Patent Form, Extent, and Effect	<p>27. (1) Each patent shall be in the prescribed form and shall be effective throughout Bangladesh.</p> <p>(2) Only one patent shall be granted for a single invention.</p>

<p>Patent Duration, Annual Fees, and Patent Restoration</p>	<p>28. (1) Subject to the provisions of this section, any patent shall remain in force for up to 20 (twenty) years from the filing date of the patent application or, if applicable, from the priority date, provided it has not expired or lost its effectiveness.</p> <p>(2) A patent may be renewed for the following year by paying the annual fee for the previous year.</p> <p>(3) In case of delay in payment of the annual fee, the time for renewal can be extended by up to 3 (three) months, subject to the submission of an application for extension and the payment of a late fee.</p> <p>(4) Notwithstanding anything in the patent or this Act, if the renewal fee is not paid within the prescribed period or within the extended period, the effectiveness of the patent will be canceled.</p> <p>(5) Notwithstanding any other applicable laws, if the effectiveness of a patent is canceled due to non-payment of the renewal fee within the prescribed period or the extended period, the patent holder will no longer have any rights to the protection of the patent's subject matter.</p> <p>(6) If the Director General is satisfied that, due to reasonable cause, it was not possible to pay the renewal fee within the prescribed period, an application for restoration of the patent may be filed within 2 (two) years after the expiry of the renewal fee payment period, upon payment of the prescribed renewal fee and restoration fee.</p>
<p>Patent Grant Subject to Special Conditions</p>	<p>29. A patent under this Act shall be granted subject to the condition that, in the case of a pharmaceutical product, the pharmaceutical product may only be imported by the government for its own use or for distribution to any dispensary, hospital, or other medical institutions operated by the government or on behalf of the government. The government may determine, through a notification in the official Gazette, that such dispensaries, hospitals, or medical institutions provide public services on behalf of the government.</p>
<p>Transfer of Patent in Case of Illegal Use of Biological Resources</p>	<p>30. (1) In the case of a patent related to biological resources that has been filed or accepted, any party with an interest in the patent may claim a share of the ownership of the patent.</p> <p>(2) To transfer the share of the patent ownership, an application must be made to the Director General, specifying the name of the relevant agency or entity.</p> <p>(3) For the purpose of this section, the share of patent ownership to be transferred shall be no less than 20 (twenty) percent.</p>

**Change of
Ownership or
Assignment of
Patent, License
Agreement, etc.**

31. (1) Any change in the ownership of a patent or any change mentioned in its application must be in writing and recorded at the office of the Director General, based on an application by the party concerned, unless a contrary application is made. The Director General will publish the change by notification on the website or in any other prescribed manner. Such a change will not be effective against any third party until it is recorded.

(2) Any license agreement or related application concerning a patent must be submitted to the Director General.

(3) The Director General will record the applications received under subsections (1) and (2), but their contents must remain confidential, and no related comments shall be published. The license agreement will not be effective against any third party before being recorded.

(4) In the following cases, certain restrictive conditions may be avoided, as follows:

- (a) Any agreement related to the sale, lease, or any other contract concerning a patented product or a product produced by a patented process; or
- (b) A license to produce or use a patented product; or
- (c) A license to use a patented process cannot legally include conditions such as:
 - i. Requiring the buyer, lessee, or licensee to refrain from accepting products other than the patented product or product produced by the patented process, or to refrain from accepting any amount or manner of goods from any person;
 - ii. Prohibiting the buyer, lessee, or licensee from accepting products other than the patented product or product produced by the patented process, or prohibiting the acceptance of any amount or manner of goods from any person;
 - iii. Requiring the buyer, lessee, or licensee to refrain from using any product other than the patented product or product produced by the patented process, or prohibiting the acceptance of any amount or manner of goods from any person;
 - iv. Prohibiting the buyer, lessee, or licensee from using any process other than the patented process or limiting the use or scope of any product other than the patented product.

(5) In a case of patent infringement, it shall be considered a defense to prove that such a contract, which includes conditions prohibited under subsection (4), was in effect at the time of infringement, unless the plaintiff is not a party to the contract and can demonstrate to the satisfaction of the court that the restrictive conditions were included without their knowledge or consent, whether express or implied.

(6) If the Director General is satisfied that the conditions mentioned in subsection (4) exist in a rights-related contract or any legal document referred to therein, he may refuse to record the change in patent ownership or the license agreement. However, if any party or both parties request a hearing, the Director General shall hear the parties concerned and resolve the matter in accordance with the relevant evidence presented, within the prescribed time and manner.

(7) Any party, or both parties, may appeal against the decision of the Director General not to record the agreement, within 2 (two) months from the date of such a decision.

(8) Any restrictions imposed on the assignee or licensee, which are not related to the registration of licensed rights or necessary for the protection of the rights, shall be considered abusive or anti-competitive.

(9) Unless otherwise provided, the following conditions or clauses shall be considered invalid:

- (a) The licensee must provide a transfer of power to the licensor for any improvement or modified use of the licensed invention, unless such a transfer is made under the same conditions specified in the licensing agreement;
- (b) Imposing any additional obligations on the licensee or assignee for intellectual property (such as patents, designs, trademarks, etc.) acquired from the licensor or any additional payment for such intellectual property;
- (c) Creating an obstacle to the licensee or assignee raising an objection to the validity of the licensed rights or transferred rights;
- (d) Imposing obligations on the licensee concerning the use of the invention after the expiration of the protection period or if the patent does not cover the invention;
- (e) Requiring the licensee or assignee to acquire raw materials or any other product or service for the use of the invention, which is not covered by the claims of the licensed invention;

	<p>(f) Imposing conditions that limit or prohibit the development or use of any technology, whether or not it is within the scope of intellectual property rights.</p> <p>(10) Unless otherwise provided, the following provisions shall be included in any assignment or license agreement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) The scope, geographical area, and term of use of the patent; (b) Conditions to ensure the quality of the product and service; (c) Obligations of the licensee to refrain from any action that could harm the ownership or reputation of the patented subject matter. <p>(11) If the subject matter of an assignment or license agreement is annulled after the contract has come into effect, the contract shall terminate immediately. The parties may recover any monetary compensation or benefits provided under the contract, unless the party receiving the benefits was acting in good faith and has derived advantages from the contract, and the termination does not cancel such benefits.</p> <p>(12) The provisions of subsection (9), along with necessary modifications, shall also apply to agreements regarding the transfer of pending patent applications and the granting of licenses.</p>
<p>Cancellation of Patent</p>	<p>32. (1) Any concerned party may file an application in court for the cancellation of a patent.</p> <p>(2) If the applicant proves that the necessary conditions under Section 8, subsections (3) and (4) were not met, or if the patent holder is not the inventor or the rightful heir of the patent, the appropriate court may cancel the patent.</p> <p>(3) In the case of cancellation of a part of the invention, only the relevant claim or claims shall be cancelled.</p> <p>(4) Any patent or part of a claim declared cancelled shall be considered cancelled from the date of the patent grant, and it will be treated as if it was never granted.</p> <p>(5) In the case of a dispute over patent rights, the concerned party may apply to the appropriate court for the transfer of the patent rights, instead of seeking cancellation of the patent.</p>

	<p>(6) The final decision of the court shall be notified to the Director General, and upon notification, the decision will be recorded and published in the prescribed manner.</p> <p>(7) After receiving an application from the patent holder, the Director General shall cancel the patent according to the existing rules and regulations concerning patents.</p> <p>(8) After receiving an application from the patent holder, the Director General shall remove the patent rights and withdraw the patent in accordance with the existing rules and regulations.</p>
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Chapter Six

Revocation of Patent

<p>Revocation of Patent</p>	<p>33. (1) Subject to the provisions of this Act, a patent may be revoked by a District Court under the following circumstances, upon petition by any person or government, or as a counterclaim in a patent infringement suit, regardless of whether the patent was granted before or after the enactment of this law:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) If the invention claimed in the complete specification is found to be fully claimed in the valid claims of an earlier patent in Bangladesh with an earlier priority date. (b) If the invention was granted to an applicant who is not entitled to apply under this Act. (c) If the patent has been unjustly obtained, infringing upon the rights of the petitioner. (d) If the claimed invention in the complete specification does not qualify as an invention under Section 2(6) of this Act. (e) If the claimed invention was already known to the public or in use by the public prior to the priority date of the claim, or disclosed in any document referred to in Section 23, making it unoriginal as per the definition in Section 2(10). (f) If the claimed invention is obvious or does not involve an inventive step as per Section 2(7) of this Act. (g) If the invention does not meet the criteria of being industrially applicable under Section 2(2) or lacks utility. (h) If the complete specification fails to provide clear instructions for carrying out the invention, particularly for individuals with
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	<p>ordinary skill in the relevant field in Bangladesh, or does not disclose the best-known method of performing the invention.</p> <p>(i) If any claim in the complete specification is insufficiently or unclearly defined or is not supported by the disclosure in the specification.</p> <p>(j) If the patent was acquired through false or misleading statements or omissions.</p> <p>(k) If the subject matter of the complete specification is deemed non-patentable under Section 6.</p> <p>(l) If the complete specification fails to disclose the biological or geographical source of any biological material used in the invention, or if it is incorrectly disclosed.</p> <p>(m) If the invention claimed is based on traditional knowledge, oral or otherwise, that is available within local or indigenous communities in Bangladesh or elsewhere.</p> <p>(2) Notice of any petition for patent revocation under this section shall be given to the Director General, who shall notify all individuals appearing to be patentees or having a share or interest in the patent. There is no requirement to notify any other individuals.</p>
<p>Revocation of Patent in Public Interest</p>	<p>34. If the government deems that any patent or its methods are detrimental to public health or the public interest, the government, after giving the patent holder an opportunity to be heard, may declare the revocation of the patent through a notification in the official gazette. Upon such declaration, the patent will be considered revoked immediately.</p>

Chapter Seven

Patent Enforcement, Compulsory Licensing, and Government Use

<p>General Principles for Implementing Patent Innovations</p>	<p>35. Without prejudice to any provisions of this Act, the following considerations shall generally apply when exercising the powers provided in this chapter:</p> <p>(a) Patents shall be granted to encourage innovation, to ensure that the invention is effectively utilized on a commercial basis within Bangladesh, and that it remains available for practical use without undue delay;</p>
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (b) A patent shall not be granted solely to enable the patent holder to enjoy exclusive rights solely for the importation of the patented product; (c) Patent protection and enforcement shall foster the advancement of new technology, the transfer and dissemination of technology, ensuring mutual benefits for both producers and users of technology, and should contribute to social and economic welfare by balancing rights and obligations; (d) The granted patent shall not obstruct the protection of public health and nutrition and shall actively contribute to advancing public interests, especially in sectors essential for Bangladesh’s socio-economic and technological progress; (e) The granted patent shall not create barriers to public health protection in any form; (f) Patents shall not be misused by the patent holder or by any person holding rights or interests in the patent from them, and such practices shall not develop in a way that unreasonably restricts commerce or adversely affects international technology transfer; and (g) Patents shall be granted to ensure that the outcomes of the patented invention are accessible to the public at an affordable price.
<p>Compulsory Licensing</p>	<p>36. (1) Any person may apply for a compulsory license at any time in the following situations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) If it is deemed necessary for the public interest, particularly for national security, nutrition, health, or national economic development; b) If any court or executive authority determines that the patent holder or licensee has engaged in an anti-competitive practice regarding the use of the invention. <i>Explanation:</i> For the purposes of this clause, anti-competitive practice includes the misuse of dominant market position or refusal to license on reasonable and fair terms. c) If there is an abuse of exclusive rights by the patent holder. <i>Explanation:</i> For the purposes of this clause, abuse of exclusive rights includes the following situations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. The patented invention fails to meet reasonable public demand; ii. The invention is not available to the public at an affordable price; iii. The patented invention is not operationally effective within Bangladesh without importation, and the patent holder has

	<p>failed to demonstrate that it is economically or technically feasible to produce it locally, either fully or partially;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">iv. The subject matter of a second patent application claims an invention that is economically significant, technically advanced, and closely related to the first patented invention, yet cannot be utilized without infringing on the first patent;v. The patent holder refuses to grant a license without reasonable grounds within a maximum of four months from the date of application;vi. Access to essential services, including the production and distribution of fixed-dose combination medicines, is restricted. <p>(2) Upon receipt of an application under sub-section (1), the Director General may grant a compulsory license subject to necessary conditions and must consider and dispose of the application within six months from the date of submission.</p> <p>(3) If an application is submitted under sub-section (1), the applicant shall endeavor to obtain a license from the patent holder on commercially reasonable terms, and if such efforts fail within a reasonable time, this condition shall not apply in cases under clause (b) of sub-section (1).</p> <p>(4) In cases of inoperability or inadequate operability of a patented product under clause (c) of sub-section (1), no compulsory license may be granted for four years from the patent application date or three years from the grant date, whichever period is later, unless the patent holder provides a reasonable explanation for such inactivity or inadequacy.</p> <p>(5) A compulsory license granted under sub-section (4) shall not be exclusive, nor shall it be transferable, even through sub-licensing, except for the transfer of part of the business or goodwill in connection with which the license is utilized.</p> <p>(6) Use of the invention under a compulsory license shall primarily be for supplying the domestic market of Bangladesh, unless the license is granted under clause (b) of sub-section (1) to address anti-competitive practices, or unless the license aims to export to foreign territories that lack or have inadequate production capability under section 39.</p> <p>(7) For semiconductor technology, a compulsory license shall only be granted by the Director General for non-commercial use or in cases where a court or legally constituted body determines that the patent</p>
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	<p>holder or licensee has engaged in anti-competitive practices and the government is satisfied that compulsory licensing is the only remedy.</p> <p>(8) In the event that a compulsory license is granted under clause (iv) of sub-section (1):</p> <p>(a) The holder of the first patent shall be entitled to a license on reasonable terms to use the invention claimed in the second patent; and</p> <p>(b) Licensing of the first patent shall not be granted without the license for the second patent.</p>
<p>Procedure for Granting Compulsory Licenses</p>	<p>37. (1) Upon receipt of an application under section 36, the Director General shall notify the patent applicant or patent holder by providing them with a copy of the application.</p> <p>(2) If the patent applicant or patent holder intends to oppose the application, they may submit a notice of opposition within the specified period.</p> <p>(3) If a notice of opposition is submitted, the Director General shall inform the applicant for the compulsory license and shall provide both the applicant and the opposing party an opportunity to be heard before resolving the matter within the timeframe mentioned in sub-section (2) of section 36.</p> <p>(4) When a compulsory license is granted under sub-section (2) of section 36, the Director General shall determine appropriate remuneration to be paid to the patent holder, which shall not exceed 4% of total sales, and set any other necessary conditions.</p> <p>(5) If a decision is made under clause (b) of sub-section (1) of section 36, the determination of remuneration shall consider any remedial actions taken by the licensee to rectify the anti-competitive use of the patent.</p> <p>(6) Upon application by the patent holder, if the Director General is satisfied that the conditions justifying the compulsory license have ceased to exist and are unlikely to recur, or that the compulsory licensee has failed to comply with the terms of the license, the Director General may, subject to adequate protection of the compulsory licensee's legal interests, cancel the compulsory license. However, before canceling the license, the licensee must be given an opportunity to be heard.</p>

<p style="text-align: center;">Compulsory License through Notification</p>	<p>38. Notwithstanding anything contained in sub-section (2) of section 36, if the government is satisfied that a national emergency or other extreme urgent circumstances exist, or if a compulsory license is deemed necessary by the government for non-commercial use of the patent after the sealing of the patent, the government may, by notification in the official gazette, issue a declaration to this effect, and the following provisions shall apply:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) After the notification is issued, at any time, the Director General may, upon application from any interested party and under such conditions as he may deem appropriate, grant a license in favor of the applicant. (b) In granting a license under this section, the Director General shall make efforts to ensure that the products produced under the license are made available to the public at affordable prices. (c) The provisions under sub-section (3) of section 36 and the procedures under sub-sections (1), (2), and (3) of section 37 shall not apply when granting a license under this section. (d) Any application filed under this section shall be disposed of within 60 (sixty) days, and in such cases, as soon as possible, the licensee shall be informed of the Director General's decision. <p>Explanation: For the purposes of this section, the term “circumstances” shall include international public health emergencies under the International Health Regulations, public health crises, such as AIDS, HIV, tuberculosis, malaria, or other pandemics, as well as non-communicable diseases like cancer, diabetes, cardiovascular disorders, or similar diseases, which will be considered in the context of granting a license for vaccines.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Compulsory License for Export of Patent-Protected Pharmaceutical Products</p>	<p>39. A compulsory license for the export of pharmaceutical products shall be granted in the following cases:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) In countries where the production of pharmaceutical products is insufficient or where there is no production capacity, a compulsory license shall be granted for the production, marketing, or export of the patent-protected pharmaceutical product. Provided, however, that such countries must grant a compulsory license or, as applicable, authorize the import of patent-protected pharmaceutical products from Bangladesh through a notification.

	<p>(b) The Director General shall grant a compulsory license solely for the production and export of the pharmaceutical product in question after receiving an application in the prescribed manner.</p> <p>(c) Pharmaceutical products produced under the compulsory license provisions in clauses (a) and (b) may be exported in accordance with other applicable provisions of this law.</p> <p>Explanation: For the purposes of this section, “pharmaceutical product” refers to any patent-protected pharmaceutical product, or any pharmaceutical product produced through a patented process, which is necessary to address public health issues. This includes the components for producing the product and diagnostic kits for diseases.</p> <p>(d) The provisions of sub-section (4) of section 40 shall apply</p>
<p>Government's Authority to Use Invention</p>	<p>40. (1) Notwithstanding anything in this Act, after a patent application is filed or a patent is granted, the government or any person authorized by it may, at any time, use the invention in accordance with the provisions of this section, if necessary for governmental purposes.</p> <p>Explanation: "Governmental purposes" refers to the public interest, public health, nutrition, environment, the existing demand for the patented product, the high price of the patented product, and the provision of pharmaceutical products for any government-registered healthcare services.</p> <p>(2) Despite the provisions of sub-section (1), any person may apply to the government for authorization to use the invention for governmental purposes under sub-section (1). In such cases, within 60 (sixty) days of the application, a decision will be made after providing the applicant and the patent holder an opportunity to be heard, along with reasons for the decision.</p> <p>(3) In the case of any invention, whether before or after the grant of the patent, the government may authorize the use of the invention, and it may grant the right to any person, whether directly or indirectly authorized by the applicant or patent holder, to produce, use, practice, or sell the invention or to import any equipment, tools, or other products, medicines, or drugs covered by the patent.</p> <p>(4) The government will pay the patent holder a reasonable royalty, which shall not exceed 4% (four percent) of the sale price for the use of the invention.</p>

<p>Additional Provisions Regarding Compulsory Licenses</p>	<p>41. (1) If a compulsory license is issued under any of Sections 36, 37, 38, 39, or 40, the applicant or the patent holder may be directed to provide relevant information, equipment, necessary dossiers, test results, or other data required for the production, use, sale, proposal, import, or export of the patented subject matter.</p> <p>(2) If the patent applicant or holder refuses to comply with any request under sub-section (1), a regulatory agency or any other government authority or institution that possesses such relevant information, equipment, necessary dossiers, test results, or other data may be directed to provide it.</p>
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Chapter Eight

Utility Model Patent

<p>Definition of Utility Model Patent and Excluded Items from Its Protection</p>	<p>42. (1) “<i>Utility Model Patent</i>” means a patent right granted by the government, associated with the structure or shape of a product or combination, suitable for use in industry, that demonstrates an advancement in technology, is outside the scope of prior art, and is registered under this Act.</p> <p>(2) The following items shall be excluded from protection as utility models, namely:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) Any process or method of a device; (b) Theories or discoveries; (c) Independent computer programs; (d) If the claimed subject matter falls under biotechnology, microbiology, pharmaceutical, or agrochemical compositions prohibited by this Act; (e) Items detrimental to public health or contrary to public order and morality; (f) Any structure, chemical compound, liquid ballast, or granular product for roads that does not maintain a specific shape; (g) A known object with a new use, including any application or natural biological material obtained by inheritance, whether in whole or in part; (h) Any invention of a process or product prohibited under this Act; (i) Plants and animals, in whole or in part, whether transformed or not, seeds, or any naturally occurring biological resource, in full or in part, even if refined, separated, or modified from such source;
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	<p>(j) Any product or material obtained by the combination or mixture of multiple additions or components that merely consolidates the properties of those elements;</p> <p>(k) Arrangement, reproduction, or replication of multiple known devices where each independently operates under any known method.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Other Conditions for Utility Model Patents</p>	<p>43. (1) Any individual or inventor may apply for a utility model patent.</p> <p>(2) The request must be submitted in the prescribed form, properly filled out, and accompanied by the fee, along with a statement.</p> <p>(3) The application for a utility model patent shall be made in the form of claims, and each claim shall be clear, concise, and supported by a complete description.</p> <p>(4) If the application complies with general and technical requirements, it shall be published on the Directorate’s website or through customary methods.</p> <p>(5) Where priority is claimed for the utility model patent, the priority date shall be deemed effective.</p> <p>(6) An examination must be conducted to assess novelty, industrial applicability, and whether the utility model patent is eligible for registration, along with compliance with all conditions and provisions described in this Act and the rules framed under it. Upon the applicant's request or based on the examination report, the application may be amended following procedures set forth in the rules. The application may be registered or rejected according to the examination report.</p> <p>(7) Where a third party opposes the registration of a utility model patent, that party or parties must submit sufficient information and evidence supporting the opposition. Based on the information and evidence received, a report shall be prepared, and if applicable, a hearing will be conducted. The Director General shall make an appropriate decision in their discretion.</p> <p>(8) The term of registration for a utility model patent shall be 8 (eight) years, renewable, effective from the date of application submission or, as applicable, from the priority date.</p> <p>(9) Other matters related to utility model patents shall be determined by rules.</p>

Chapter Nine

Enforcement of Patent Rights

Enforcement of Patent Rights	<p>44. (1) If any person, without entering into an agreement with the patent holder and subject to the provisions of this Act, infringes any rights declared under Section 25, the patent holder may file a lawsuit against that person for such infringement of rights.</p> <p>(2) If-</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) any exclusive licensee, compulsory licensee, or non-exclusive licensee fails to specifically enforce the terms of the agreement, such licensee may file a lawsuit against the patent holder for specific enforcement of the contract; (b) any exclusive licensee, compulsory licensee, or non-exclusive licensee violates the terms of the license granted, the patent holder may file a lawsuit against the licensee for specific enforcement of the contract; (c) in cases where there is a violation of the terms mentioned in clauses (a) and (b), the court may grant an injunction in favor of the licensee or patent holder for the protection of their rights; (d) if the court is satisfied that a party has breached the terms of the license, causing damage to the other party, the court may order the breaching party to pay compensation to the injured party. <p>(3) A civil court, or any court with jurisdiction under the Civil Procedure Code or other relevant laws, may issue an order for a breach of the provisions of Section 25:</p> <p>Provided that, if the defendant raises a counterclaim for patent revocation, the court shall adjudicate both the infringement lawsuit and the counterclaim together.</p>
Jurisdiction	<p>45. Any lawsuit under Section 44 may only be filed in an appropriate court that is not subordinate to the District Court.</p>
Burden of Proof	<p>46. (1) If the subject matter of a patent holder’s rights infringement involves a product obtained through a patented process, the court may order the infringer to prove that the process they used to produce an identical product is different from the patented process.</p>

	<p>(2) If an identical product is produced without the consent of the patent holder, it shall be presumed, unless proven otherwise, that the product was obtained through the patented process, provided that the patented process yields a new product.</p> <p>(3) When determining whether a party has complied with an order under subsection (1), the court shall not order disclosure of any manufacturing or business secrets, if the court deems such an order unreasonable.</p>
<p>Injunction</p>	<p>47. (1) In the event of a suit under Section 44 for breach of contract or specific performance, the court shall not issue any ex parte interim or temporary injunction.</p> <p>(2) Before passing any judgment in a case related to patent rights infringement or specific performance of a contract, the court shall provide an opportunity for the other party to be heard.</p> <p>(3) The court may issue an interim or temporary injunction based on the following factors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Preliminary evidence, balance of convenience, and irreparable harm favoring the applicant or patent holder; b) In cases concerning pharmaceutical products or processes, the impact of the injunction on the availability of the product for medical use shall be considered; c) Failure to provide a security bond or equivalent assurance to protect the interests of the opposing party. <p><i>Provided that the court shall not grant an interim injunction without giving the opposing party an opportunity to be heard.</i></p> <p>(4) Applications for temporary injunctions must be resolved within 30 (thirty) days of submission.</p> <p>(5) The aggrieved party may file for a reconsideration of the temporary injunction within 14 (fourteen) days of being informed of it.</p> <p>(6) If, after issuing a temporary injunction, the court determines that no infringement of patent terms has occurred or is likely to occur, the court may, upon request from the opposing party, order the applicant to compensate for any damage caused by the issuance of the temporary injunction.</p>

	<p>(7) The court shall not grant a temporary injunction or specific relief for a violation of the terms stated in Section 44 under the following circumstances, without affecting the order of compensation:</p> <p>(a) After patent grant, if the plaintiff or an authorized person has not:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. Taken the necessary steps to produce the patented product in Bangladesh; ii. Commercially utilized the patented invention; iii. Utilized the patented invention in a manner incapable of meeting market demand in a quality-assured way; <p>(b) If there is a risk of significant harm to the public interest;</p> <p>(c) If the patented product or product produced through the patented process is sold at a price exceeding the average purchasing power of consumers by the plaintiff or with the plaintiff's consent;</p> <p>(d) If the patented product fails to meet specific consumer demands;</p> <p>(e) If the patented product is sold at an excessive price due to the presence or absence of competing products in the market;</p> <p>(f) If the patent was obtained by the plaintiff in violation of any provision of this Act.</p> <p>(8) If a patent right is infringed by a government agency or due to the provision of government services, the court shall not issue an injunction, except where necessary to obtain evidence under the control of the infringer, without affecting the determination of damages.</p>
<p>Limitations on the Court's Power to Grant Injunctions</p>	<p>48. No temporary, interim, or permanent injunction may be issued against any act done under Sections 29, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, and 41 of this Act.</p>
<p>Court Remedies</p>	<p>49. 1. In cases of breach of contract, the court may grant permanent injunctions along with compensation or an account of profits as remedies.</p> <p>2. Subject to the provisions of sub-section (1), the court shall determine the amount of compensation in cases of patent rights infringement based on its discretion.</p> <p>3. In determining the compensation for patent infringement, the court may consider the following factors:</p>

	<p>(a) The date on which the registration was published in the government notice, website, or customary channels.</p> <p>(b) The date on which the applicant notified the infringer about the patent application.</p> <p>(c) The date on which the infringer became aware of the patent application.</p> <p>(d) Whether the patented product is available at a fair price.</p> <p>(e) Whether the patented product is produced in Bangladesh.</p> <p>(f) Whether the patent holder has suffered irreparable damage.</p> <p>(g) Whether there has been any adverse impact on local industries or products.</p> <p>4. If, in a patent infringement case, the defendant is willing and prepared to take a license under the terms set by the court, no permanent injunction shall be issued against them. In such cases, the court will set the appropriate royalty and other necessary conditions for the license.</p> <p>5. Unless proven otherwise, the court will take steps to protect the legal rights and business confidentiality of the patent infringer.</p>
<p>Defense in Patent Infringement Cases</p>	<p>50. 1. In patent infringement cases, any grounds for revocation of the patent under Section 33 can be used as a defense by the defendant.</p> <p>2. In cases of patent infringement related to the manufacture, use, or import of any product or machinery, or the use of a method, or the import, use, or distribution of medical equipment or medicines, the defendant may base their defense on the argument that the manufacturing, use, import, or distribution was done in accordance with one or more conditions outlined in Sections 29, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, and 43 of this Act.</p>
<p>Scientific Adviser</p>	<p>51. 1. In cases of patent infringement or any proceedings under this Act, the court may, at any time, with or without the submission of a formal application, appoint an independent or impartial adviser to assist or investigate for the purpose of providing a report, except when the issue concerns a legal question or the interpretation of the law.</p>

	2. The court will determine the remuneration of the scientific adviser, which will include the costs of preparing the report and the appropriate daily fee for the adviser if they are required to appear before the court on a specific day.
Appeal Against Administrative Orders, etc.	52. Under this Act, any decision made by the Director General, particularly concerning the granting of a compulsory license and decisions related to the remuneration for such a license, must be appealed to the High Court Division of the Supreme Court within 2 (two) months from the date of the decision.

Chapter Ten

Filing of Lawsuits, Procedures, and Penalties

Application of Civil Procedure Code	53. Subject to the other provisions of this Act, the provisions of the Civil Procedure Code shall apply in the filing of lawsuits, legal procedures, and the functioning of the courts under this Act.
Compensation	<p>54. (1) If any person fails to comply with any order issued under this Act, the court may, based on the circumstances and context of the case, order compensation or take any other appropriate action.</p> <p>(2) If any person creates or causes to be created a false entry in any registration document reserved under this Act, or records any matter with the intent of providing a copy of such false entry, it will be considered a violation of this Act, and the person will be ordered to pay compensation of up to 50,000 (fifty thousand) Taka.</p> <p>(3) If any person falsely claims that the product sold or the process used by them is patented in Bangladesh or has been applied for a patent in Bangladesh, it will be considered a violation of this Act, and the person will be ordered to pay compensation of up to 50,000 (fifty thousand) Taka.</p> <p>(4) If any person uses the expression "Patent, Industrial Designs and Trademarks Department" or any other words in their business or any document or in any manner that might lead to the belief that their business or premises are authorized for patent registration, it will be considered a</p>

	<p>violation of this Act, and the person will be ordered to pay compensation of up to 50,000 (fifty thousand) Taka.</p> <p>(5) If any company violates such provisions, each responsible person within the company and those engaged in the operation of the company will be considered as violating the provisions of this Act, and legal proceedings will be initiated against them accordingly.</p>
<p>Special Court, Appeal, etc.</p>	<p>55. (1) For the purpose of fulfilling the objectives of this Act, the government may, through a notification in the official gazette, establish a special court for matters related to patents. Until such a special court is established, the court competent to settle cases or legal proceedings regarding patent infringement under the <i>Patents and Designs Act, 1911</i> shall be considered the appropriate court.</p> <p>(2) An appeal may be filed against the judgment issued by the special court or the competent court under sub-section (1) within 2 (two) months from the date of the judgment.</p>

Chapter Eleven

Powers of the Director-General

<p>Powers of the Director-General as a Civil Court</p>	<p>56. Subject to the rules framed for this purpose, the Director-General shall have the powers of a civil court with respect to the following matters:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) Issuing summons to any person, compelling their attendance, and examining them under oath; (b) Directing the production and submission of documents; (c) Taking testimony through affidavits; (d) Issuing commissions for the examination of witnesses or documents; (e) Ordering the payment of costs; (f) Reconsidering their own decisions upon receiving an application within a specified time and in the prescribed manner; (g) Revoking any ex parte orders upon receiving an application within a specified time and in the prescribed manner; (h) Any other matter as prescribed.
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<p>Correction of Clerical Errors and Extension of Time</p>	<p>57. (1) The Director-General, without affecting the patent application or the complete specification as described in Sections 11 and 12 of this Act, may, upon the applicant's request and upon payment of the prescribed fee, correct any clerical errors, mistakes, or errors in translation or interpretation in any document filed by the applicant for patent registration under the law.</p> <p>(2) The Director-General may, unless otherwise provided in this Act, extend the time for the completion of any action or legal procedure, as per the provisions of this Act and the rules made under it, based on a written application.</p> <p>(3) The Director-General shall notify the concerned parties and set the conditions, and in the event of a delay beyond the prescribed time, may grant additional time upon the payment of the prescribed fee, based on the application of any party.</p>
<p>Testimony Procedure and Powers of the Controller</p>	<p>58. Subject to the provisions of any rules made in this regard, in any proceedings presented to the Director-General under this Act, unless otherwise directed by him, testimony shall be provided through an affidavit. However, in any case, if the Director-General deems it appropriate, he may accept oral testimony in place of, or alongside, the affidavit, or may cross-examine any party regarding the contents of the affidavit.</p>
<p>Exercise of Powers</p>	<p>59. The Director-General, in accordance with the provisions of this Act or any rules made thereunder, may exercise the powers entrusted to him. However, unless otherwise provided in this Act, before making any adverse decision against any party under these powers, the concerned party must be given an opportunity to be heard.</p>

Chapter Twelve

Exceptions

<p>Parallel Importation of Patent Products</p>	<p>60. (1) International exhaustion policy shall apply in the case of Bangladesh.</p> <p>(2) The parallel importation of a patented product, introduced in the market of any country by any person, shall not be considered as a violation of patent law in Bangladesh.</p>
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<p>Special Provisions on Patents</p>	<p>61. The rights granted under section 25 of this Act shall not apply in the case of any act related to the production, construction, use, sale, import, or export of a patented product, where the act is subject to the submission of information under any law governing the production, use, sale, import, or export of goods related to developments, whether in Bangladesh or any other country.</p>
<p>Exemption Due to Research Exception and Other Limitations</p>	<p>62. The rights under a patent shall not apply in the following cases:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) Any activity carried out for personal or non-commercial purposes. (b) Any activity conducted for educational, experimental, or research purposes. (c) Any work done in a personal context, such as preparation done in a pharmacy or treatment administered by a doctor according to a prescription, including medicines or other medical treatments prepared for such purposes. (d) Any act carried out by an individual in good faith before the filing of a patent application, or if a priority date is claimed, before the date of filing of that application, involving the production or use of the claimed product or method, or preparation for the production or use of such a product in Bangladesh. (e) Temporary use of a patented invention on foreign ships, aircraft, or land vehicles within Bangladesh.

Chapter Thirteen

Miscellaneous

<p>Registration Register and Online Publication</p>	<p>63. (1) A registration register must be maintained in the Directorate under the name of the patent registration register.</p> <p>(2) The registration register shall be open for inspection by any person, and any person shall have the right to obtain a citation from the register in accordance with the provisions of this law and the rules made thereunder. The register shall be made available to the public at a convenient time.</p> <p>(3) For the purposes of this law, the Directorate shall publish all its publications on its website or in other customary means.</p>
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	<p>(4) A certified copy or excerpt of the relevant section of the registration register, bearing the seal of the Directorate, shall be provided to the applicant upon payment of the prescribed fee.</p> <p>(5) The registration register shall serve as prima facie evidence of any matter under this law, and certificates shall be signed by the Director-General, certifying that any entry made in the register, for which he has been empowered under this law or the rules made thereunder, has or has not been made, or any other matter that he is empowered to perform under this law or the rules, shall serve as prima facie evidence of the same.</p>
<p>Patent Representative</p>	<p>64. (1) In cases where the applicant's principal place of residence or place of business is outside Bangladesh, the applicant shall be represented in Bangladesh by a suitable Bangladeshi person residing in Bangladesh.</p> <p>(2) The qualifications and other conditions for registration as a patent representative shall be determined by the rules.</p>
<p>Disclosure of Information</p>	<p>65. All information related to the execution of the patent shall be kept open for public inspection without any fee, and such information shall include the following details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) The complete specification, claims, drawings, and other documents submitted by the applicant along with the full patent application; (b) Information related to the filing of the complete specification or any case where an application is considered abandoned, according to the provisional specification; (c) All information submitted under Section 15; (d) Detailed information regarding the publication of any application under Section 17; (e) Detailed information regarding any withdrawal or re-application under Section 10; (f) Information regarding any application filed for examination under Section 21; (g) Detailed reports of examination and other information related to the proceedings issued under Section 22; (h) Detailed information regarding the search for examination purposes under Section 23; (i) Information related to the acceptance or rejection of any application under Section 24; (j) Information regarding the payment of renewal fees; (k) Information regarding the expiry of a patent or its impending expiry;

	<p>(l) Information regarding any registration or application for registration in the register;</p> <p>(m) Information provided under Section 43;</p> <p>(n) Detailed information provided under Subsections (4), (5), and (6) of Section 31;</p> <p>(o) All communications, including oral and written correspondence, between the patent office and the applicant.</p>
<p>Director-General's Power to Request Information from the Patent Holder</p>	<p>66. (1) The Director-General, during the validity of the patent, may, at any time, by written notice, direct the patent holder or licensee, whether exclusive or non-exclusive, to submit information or a provisional statement regarding the commercial availability of the patented product in Bangladesh. This must be done within two (2) months of the notice or within any additional time approved by the Director-General.</p> <p>(2) Without prejudice to the provisions of subsection (1), each patent holder and licensee, whether exclusive or non-exclusive, shall, in the prescribed manner and form, and at the prescribed intervals, submit information or a provisional statement regarding the commercial availability of the patented product in Bangladesh to the Director-General.</p> <p>However, the interval between such submissions shall not be less than one (1) year.</p>
<p>Patent Representative Registration Register</p>	<p>67. The Director-General shall maintain a register known as the "Patent Representative Registration Register" in his office.</p>
<p>Issuance of Orders or Formulation of Strategy</p>	<p>68. The Government may issue necessary orders or formulate strategies to ensure the overall integrity of this law and to fulfill its objectives, without compromising its intent.</p>
<p>Removal of Difficulty</p>	<p>69. If any difficulty arises in implementing the provisions of this law, the Government may, through a notification in the official gazette, take necessary measures to remove such difficulties.</p>
<p>Power to Make Rules</p>	<p>70. For the purposes of this Act, the Government may, by notification in the official Gazette, make rules.</p>
<p>Repeal and Savings</p>	<p>71. (1) The Bangladesh Patent Act, 2022 (Act No. 5 of 2022), hereinafter referred to as the said Act, is hereby repealed.</p> <p>(2) Notwithstanding the repeal, any pending applications under the said Act shall be disposed of under the provisions of this Act.</p>

	<p>(3) The provisions of subsection (2) shall come into effect with necessary amendments and additions, and decisions made by the courts prior to the enactment of this Act shall remain preserved.</p> <p>(4) Where this Act expands or creates new rights, including with conditions for preservation, existing registrations will benefit from such expansion or creation. However, where this Act reduces or abolishes rights, existing registrations will not be effective, and they will remain valid as if this Act had not been enacted.</p> <p>Provided that, this shall not apply to decisions mentioned in subsection (3).</p> <p>(5) The activities performed by the Director-General shall be preserved in a manner that indicates they have been carried out under this Act.</p> <p>(6) Until rules are made under Section 70 of this Act, and provided that they are consistent with the provisions of this Act, the Patents and Designs Rules, 1933, which were previously enacted, shall remain in force.</p>
Publication of English Text	<p>72. After the commencement of this Act, the Government may, by notification in the official Gazette, publish an authentic English text of this Act.</p> <p>Provided that, in the event of conflict between the Bangla and the English text, the Bangla text shall prevail.</p>

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